

Illuminating Innovations: A Comprehensive Review of Lasers in Periodontics

Dr. RashmiShiwach¹, Dr. Pradeep Shukla², Dr. Shreya Bansal³, Dr. Akansha Garg⁴

¹ Reader, ²Head of the department, ³ Post graduate, ⁴ Post graduate
Dept of Periodontology and Implantology, DJ College Of Dental Sciences and Research, India

Abstract

Peridonal disease is one of the most common oral diseases and a huge part of the population suffers from this bad boy genome wide. They are inflammatory disease processes, which is harmful and leads to destruction of the periodontal & bone structure surrounding dentition thereby leading to loss teeth. The conventional method used for treatment of periodontal disease has been removal of microbial biofilms by mechanical debridement and surgery, which have provided successful results but often associated with pain, bleeding and long post- surgical healing times. With huge popularity over the last few years, laser therapy is an alternative to treat these problems in such a way that it might have substantial success and also not requiring surgical procedures.

Laser, the most powerful light known, produces a much tighter beam that can be focused on and destroy only the diseased tissue without heating the adjacent healthy tissues. Several lasers for clinical use in periodontics currently are available, including the diode, erbium-doped yttrium aluminum garnet (Er:YAG), and neodymium-doped yttrium aluminum garnet (Nd:YAG) lasers; however improvements still are being made to bring this technology to its optimal performance. The photothermal and photochemical effects that these lasers employ are among the most commonly used methods, and which alleviate pain also have anti-inflammatory properties.

There are several benefits of laser assisted periodontal therapy such as less postoperative pain and bleeding, faster recovery times over the traditional methods. Laser Technology: Lasers to aid disinfection of periodontal pockets for better success. Regrettably, the difficulties they face are that of training and capital expenses required for specialized equipment and the lack of standardized clinical protocols.

The further implementation of laser technology into periodontal practice in the future holds great potential to improve therapy for patients with periodontitis, and represents an intriguing area of ongoing research effort in oral health.

Keywords: Lasers, periodontics, periodontal disease, soft tissue surgery, hard tissue surgery, dental lasers

INTRODUCTION

Periodontal disease is the chronic inflammatory destruction of all the supporting structures of teeth, including the gums, periodontal ligament and alveolar bone. It is one of the most common oral health problems in the world, and over time it can become so serious that it results in tooth loss [1]. Severe periodontal disease afflicts about 11% of the world's adult population and is a major public health problem. It negatively affects not only oral health but also overall systemic health, including cardiovascular disease, diabetes and respiratory infections [2].

The most important cause of periodontal disease is bacterial plaque; a biofilm (also called dental plaque) that adheres to the surface of teeth. This plaque induces an inflammatory action from the neighboring periodontal tissue, and will eventually destroy it if not correctly controlled. A host immune response to these bacterial pathogens contributes to the degradation of connective tissue and alveolar bone, leading ultimately to tooth loss [3]. When left untreated, periodontal disease can even advance to tooth loss.

Figure 1: Laser Tissue interaction

Historically, treatment of periodontal disease has been centered around mechanical removal of plaque and calculus (tarter) from the tooth surface. The foundation of periodontal therapy is techniques like scaling and root planing (SRP) in which your dentist or dental hygienist manually remove plaque and tartar from beneath the gum line. When this is ineffective, surgical interventions such as flap surgery, bone grafts or guided tissue regeneration are used [4]. Although these standard treatment protocols are successful in arresting periodontal disease progression, they are associated with extensive pain, swelling, and bleeding after surgery as well as a long recovery phase.

In recent years, the field of periodontal therapy has been revolutionized by the incorporation of laser technology which is a less invasive alternative to classic mechanical techniques. Laser offers a targeted bone and gum tissue treatment area which can only destroyed as the result of laser-generated cell dehydration. Furthermore, lasers are less invasive and thus create better principium as well as part as this causes less peri-operative discomforts for the patients as well heals faster. Ishikawa et al. Lasers appear to be effective at barely a bacteria, removing debris from periodontal pockets, and tissue growth across different studies as well [5]. In addition, lasers can offer complementary efficacy when used with traditional mechanical debridement to improve overall modified treatment results.

In the field of periodontics, there are different types of lasers that come in several wavelengths and work very differently from each other. The diode lasers, the carbon dioxide (CO₂) lasers, and the erbium lasers are the most frequently used lasers. Because of its ability to preferentially target pigmented tissues, diode lasers are routinely used for soft tissue procedures like gingival contouring and pocket sterilization. CO₂ lasers, however are very efficient in vaporizing soft tissues with minimal collateral damage making them ideal for applications such as the treatment of periodontal pockets and frenectomies. Erbium lasers, due to wide range of applications of this laser, can be used not only on soft but also hard tissue procedures such as bone contouring and root debridement [5].

Table 1: Laser Mechanism and application			
Laser Type	Wavelength	Mechanism of Action	Clinical Applications
Diode Laser	810-980 nm	Selectively targets pigmented tissues, photothermal effect	Soft tissue procedures (gingival contouring, pocket sterilization, bacterial reduction)
CO₂ Laser	10,600 nm	Vaporizes soft tissues with minimal collateral damage	Soft tissue procedures (frenectomy, pocket decontamination)
Erbium Laser	2,780 nm (Er,Cr)	Ablates both soft and hard tissues, photomechanical action	Hard and soft tissue procedures (bone contouring, root debridement, tissue

	), 2,940 nm (Er)		regeneration)
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Although there is an irrefutable benefit that we find with the advent of the laser technology in the periodontal therapy, it does not come without its own set of limitations. Laser equipment is often prohibitively expensive, thereby limiting its utility in some clinical settings. Moreover, whilst lasers are useful for many periodontal therapeutic interventions, they cannot completely replace the mechanical debridement in each case. According to research, findings from some studies suggest that the long-term effects of laser treatment are yet unestablished and call for more investigation in determining whether or not it should replace conventional remedies [6].

TYPES OF LASERS IN PERIODONTICS

Several types of lasers have been incorporated into periodontal practice, each with distinct wavelengths, tissue interactions, and clinical applications. The most commonly used lasers in periodontics are diode lasers, erbium lasers, CO₂ lasers, and Nd:YAG lasers. (Nd:YAG (neodymium-doped yttrium aluminum garnet; Nd:Y₃Al₅O₁₂) is a crystal that is used as a lasing medium for solid-state lasers.)

Diode Lasers

Diode lasers, which operate in the near-infrared spectrum (810–980 nm), are widely used in soft tissue procedures. Their mechanism of action relies on high absorption by pigments like melanin and hemoglobin, making them suitable for procedures such as gingival contouring, frenectomy, and periodontal pocket decontamination [7]. These lasers cause tissue ablation through a process called photothermal interaction, where laser energy is converted to heat, leading to the vaporization of tissue.

Diode lasers offer advantages such as excellent hemostasis, reduced postoperative discomfort, and a clear surgical field due to minimal bleeding [8]. However, their main limitation is that they can only be used for soft tissue and have limited penetration depth, which can result in incomplete bacterial decontamination if used improperly [9].

Erbium Lasers (Er and Er,Cr)

Erbium lasers, including Er(2,940 nm) and Er,Cr(2,780 nm), are versatile tools used in both soft and hard tissue applications. Their mechanism of action is based on their high absorption by water, which allows for efficient ablation of both soft tissues and bone [10]. These lasers are especially useful for osseous surgery, root surface debridement, and gingival contouring.

A key advantage of erbium lasers is their minimal thermal damage, which preserves the surrounding tissue. Additionally, many procedures performed with these lasers are less invasive and require little or no anesthesia [11]. Despite these benefits, erbium lasers are expensive and require extensive training for dental professionals to operate effectively.

CO₂ Lasers

CO₂ lasers, which operate at a wavelength of 10,600 nm, are primarily used for soft tissue surgery due to their high absorption by water and their ability to vaporize tissues with minimal penetration depth [8]. These lasers are particularly effective for soft tissue procedures such as gingivectomy, frenectomy, and removal of benign oral lesions.

The CO₂ laser provides excellent hemostasis and a sterile surgical field due to its photothermal effects, which coagulate blood vessels as tissue is ablated. However, like diode lasers, CO₂ lasers are limited to soft tissue applications and have a higher potential for thermal damage if not used properly [12].

NdLasers

Ndlasers (neodymium-doped yttrium aluminum garnet) operate at a wavelength of 1,064 nm and are primarily used for periodontal decontamination and soft tissue management. Ndlasers have a high affinity for pigments like melanin, which makes them particularly effective for bacterial decontamination in periodontal pockets [13]. The laser energy is absorbed by the dark-pigmented bacteria, resulting in their destruction without harming surrounding healthy tissues.

The Ndlaser is also used for procedures such as gingival contouring and coagulation of blood vessels. However, its deeper penetration can sometimes lead to unintended damage to underlying structures if not carefully controlled.

MECHANISMS OF LASERS

Basic Principles of Laser Technology

Lasers (Light Amplification by Stimulated Emission of Radiation) function by emitting concentrated beams of light that can be precisely directed onto tissues. The specific wavelength of each laser determines its interaction with different types of tissue. The key mechanisms by which lasers affect tissues include photothermal, photochemical, and photomechanical interactions.

In periodontal therapy, the photothermal effect is most commonly utilized, where laser energy is absorbed by tissue components like water and pigments, causing rapid heating and subsequent ablation or coagulation of the tissue. This process is highly controlled, allowing for selective targeting of diseased tissues while preserving healthy structures.

APPLICATIONS OF LASERS IN PERIODONTICS

Lasers have a wide range of applications in periodontal therapy, from decontaminating periodontal pockets to performing soft and hard tissue surgeries.

Treatment of Periodontal Disease

The use of lasers in the treatment of periodontal disease has shown promising results in terms of reducing bacterial load, promoting healing, and enhancing patient comfort. Laser-assisted periodontal therapy involves the removal of diseased tissue and bacteria from periodontal pockets, promoting tissue regeneration and reducing inflammation [5].

Studies have shown that lasers can effectively reduce the depth of periodontal pockets and promote reattachment of the periodontal ligament to the tooth root, leading to improved clinical outcomes compared to traditional mechanical debridement alone.

Soft Tissue Surgery

Lasers are commonly used for soft tissue surgeries such as gingivectomy, frenectomy, and crown lengthening. These procedures benefit from the precision and minimal invasiveness of laser technology, leading to reduced bleeding and quicker healing times [8].

Hard Tissue Surgery

In addition to soft tissue management, lasers have shown significant potential in hard tissue surgeries. Hard tissue lasers, particularly erbium lasers such as Er,Cr, have been effectively used in osseous surgery and root surface debridement.

Erbium Lasers in Osseous Surgery:

These lasers are highly efficient in removing bone with minimal heat generation, which helps in preventing necrosis of the surrounding tissues [14]. Hard tissue lasers are able to selectively remove diseased bone while preserving healthy bone structures, promoting faster healing and reducing the need for invasive surgical methods like flap surgeries [15].

Root Surface Preparation:

Lasers have been shown to enhance root surface decontamination by effectively removing the bacterial biofilm without inducing damage to the underlying dentin [16]. The precise action of lasers also results in a smoother root surface, which facilitates better reattachment of periodontal tissues.

Biostimulation

Low-Level Laser Therapy (LLLT), also known as photobiomodulation, involves the use of low-energy lasers to stimulate cellular processes, promoting tissue repair, reducing inflammation, and accelerating healing [17]. In periodontal therapy, biostimulation is particularly beneficial in enhancing wound healing and managing postoperative discomfort.

Tissue Regeneration:

Research has shown that LLLT can promote the regeneration of periodontal tissues, including gingival and osseous tissues, by enhancing cellular proliferation and collagen synthesis. This property of lasers makes them a useful adjunct in regenerative periodontal procedures, including bone grafting and guided tissue regeneration [16].

Pain Management:

Lasers used at low energy levels can help reduce postoperative pain by decreasing inflammatory mediators and promoting endorphin release [8]. Patients undergoing laser periodontal therapy have reported less postoperative discomfort compared to those treated with conventional methods.

Table 2: Application of Lasers

Clinical Procedure	Laser Type	Mechanism of Action	Benefits
Gingival Contouring	Diode Laser, CO2 Laser	Photothermal effect selectively targets soft tissue	Precision, minimal bleeding, faster healing
Frenectomy	CO2 Laser, Diode Laser	Vaporizes soft tissues with minimal collateral damage	Less invasive, minimal discomfort, reduced healing time
Pocket Sterilization	Diode Laser, Nd:YAG Laser	Photothermal action destroys bacteria and decontaminates pockets	Effective bacterial reduction, minimal tissue damage
Root Debridement	Erbium Lasers (Er:YAG)	Photomechanical ablation of hard tissue	Preserves surrounding tissue, promotes tissue regeneration
Bone Contouring	Erbium Lasers (Er, Cr:YSGG)	Ablates hard tissue with minimal thermal damage	Precise bone removal, less invasive than traditional surgery
Soft Tissue Biopsy	CO2 Laser, Diode Laser	Vaporization and excision of soft tissue	Minimal bleeding, clear surgical field
Peri-implantitis Treatment	Diode Laser, Erbium Laser	Decontamination of implant surface, promotes tissue healing	Promotes healing around implants, reduces infection risk
Crown Lengthening	Diode Laser, CO2 Laser	Soft tissue removal and reshaping	Less invasive than traditional methods, faster recovery
Periodontal Pocket Reduction	Nd:YAG Laser, Diode Laser	Decontaminates and removes diseased tissue	Effective at reducing pocket depth, enhanced patient comfort
Tissue Regeneration	Erbium Laser, Low-Level Laser Therapy (LLLT)	Stimulates fibroblast proliferation and collagen synthesis	Promotes faster healing, enhances tissue regeneration

CLINICAL OUTCOMES AND ADVANTAGES OF LASER THERAPY

Numerous studies have compared the effectiveness of laser therapy with traditional periodontal treatments, with most reporting favorable outcomes in terms of reduced bleeding, decreased postoperative discomfort, and improved healing [5]). Below are key clinical outcomes associated with the use of lasers in periodontics:

Reduced Bleeding and Postoperative Discomfort

Lasers, particularly diode and CO2 lasers, provide excellent hemostasis by coagulating blood vessels during the procedure [9]. This results in reduced intraoperative bleeding, allowing for a clearer surgical field and less need for suturing.

Patients undergoing laser-assisted surgeries generally report lower levels of postoperative pain and discomfort due to the minimally invasive nature of the procedure. This is especially beneficial in soft tissue surgeries, where traditional methods often result in prolonged recovery periods [8].

Enhanced Healing

Laser therapy accelerates wound healing by stimulating fibroblast proliferation and collagen formation [14]. The photothermal effect of lasers also promotes faster epithelialization of wound sites, reducing the risk of postoperative infections and complications.

A systematic review comparing laser therapy with conventional mechanical debridement found that laser-assisted treatments were associated with faster recovery times and better clinical outcomes in terms of attachment level gains and pocket depth reduction.

Long-Term Outcomes in Periodontal Regeneration

Long-term studies on the use of lasers in periodontal regeneration suggest that laser therapy can result in sustained improvements in clinical parameters such as pocket depth reduction, attachment level gain, and bone regeneration [5]. However, the outcomes vary depending on the type of laser used and the specific procedure being performed.

LIMITATIONS AND CHALLENGES

While laser therapy offers several advantages over traditional periodontal treatments, there are some notable limitations and challenges associated with its use.

Cost and Accessibility

One of the primary limitations of laser therapy is the high cost of the equipment. Lasers, especially erbium and CO2 lasers, can be significantly more expensive than traditional surgical instruments [14]. This can limit their accessibility, particularly in smaller dental practices or in regions with limited resources.

Need for Specialized Training

Laser technology requires specialized training for dental professionals to use effectively. The precision and specificity of laser-tissue interaction mean that improper use can result in unintended tissue damage or inadequate treatment [12]. The learning curve associated with laser usage may deter some practitioners from adopting the technology in their practices.

Risks and Complications

Although lasers are generally safe when used correctly, there are some potential risks and complications associated with their use. For instance, excessive heat generation can cause thermal damage to surrounding tissues, leading to delayed healing or even necrosis. Additionally, improper use of lasers in hard tissue procedures can lead to damage to the tooth structure or underlying bone.

FUTURE DIRECTIONS IN LASER TECHNOLOGY

The future of laser therapy in periodontics lies in ongoing advancements in laser technology and its integration with other therapeutic modalities. Several areas of research and innovation hold promise for improving the efficacy and accessibility of laser-based treatments.

Innovations in Laser Technology

Research is underway to develop lasers with enhanced precision and reduced energy requirements. These next-generation lasers are expected to offer even greater control over tissue interactions, reducing the risk of thermal damage and improving clinical outcomes.

Combination with Regenerative Therapies

One of the most exciting prospects in laser therapy is its combination with regenerative treatments, such as stem cell therapy and growth factor application. Studies have shown that lasers can enhance the effects of regenerative procedures by promoting tissue repair and reducing inflammation. Future research is likely to focus on optimizing these combinations to achieve superior clinical results in periodontal regeneration.

Addressing Research Gaps

Although significant progress has been made in understanding the applications of lasers in periodontics, there remain several research gaps. Long-term clinical trials are needed to evaluate the durability of laser-assisted periodontal regeneration, particularly in comparison to traditional method. Additionally, more research is required to determine the optimal laser settings for various procedures to ensure consistency and safety across different patient populations.

CONCLUSION

Laser technology has revolutionized periodontics by offering a minimally invasive, precise, and effective alternative to traditional treatments for periodontal disease. Various types of lasers, such as diode, CO₂, erbium, and Nd, provide targeted solutions for both soft and hard tissue procedures, from gingival contouring and frenectomy to bone contouring and pocket decontamination. Their precision allows for selective targeting of diseased tissues while preserving healthy areas, resulting in reduced pain, bleeding, and faster recovery times. Furthermore, lasers enhance tissue regeneration and bacterial reduction, leading to improved clinical outcomes. Despite these advantages, challenges such as high equipment costs and the need for specialized training limit their broader adoption. While lasers complement traditional methods, they cannot fully replace mechanical debridement in all cases, and further research is required to assess long-term outcomes. Overall, lasers have transformed periodontal therapy, providing patients with better care and potentially shaping the future of dental treatments as technology continues to advance.

REFERENCES

1. Eke PI, Dye BA, Wei L, Thornton-Evans GO, Genco RJ. Prevalence of periodontitis in adults in the United States: J Dent Res. 2012;91(10):914-20.
2. Ciurescu, C. E., Dima, L., Ciurescu, V. A., Noja, G. G., Istodor, A. V., Moga, M. A., Ardelean, L. C., Rusu, L. C., Leretter, M. T. Laser Therapy Effects on Periodontal Status: A Randomized Study Using Gaussian Network Analysis and Structural Equation Modeling Approach. Medicina (Kaunas, Lithuania), 2024;60(3):437-440.
3. Pihlstrom BL, Michalowicz BS, Johnson NW. Periodontal diseases. The Lancet. 2005;366(9499):1809-1820.
4. Schwarz F, Aoki A, Sculean A, Becker J. Laser application in non-surgical periodontal therapy: A systematic review. J Clin Periodontol. 2008;35:29-44.
5. Ishikawa I, Aoki A, Takasaki AA. Potential applications of Erbium laser in periodontics. J Periodontal Res. 2009;44:585-591.
6. Sgolastra F, Petrucci A, Severino M, Gatto R, Monaco A. Lasers for nonsurgical periodontal therapy: a meta-analysis. J Dent. 2013;41(3):273-285.

7. Aoki, A., Sasaki, K. M., Watanabe, H., Ishikawa, I. Lasers in nonsurgical periodontal therapy. *Periodontology* 2000, 36:59–97.
8. Moritz A, Schoop U, Goharkhay K. Treatment of periodontal pockets with a diode laser. *Lasers Surg Med.* 1999;25(1):13-25.
9. Kamma, J. J., Vasdekis, V. G., Romanos, G. E. The effect of diode laser (980 nm) treatment on aggressive periodontitis: evaluation of microbial and clinical parameters. *Photomedicine and laser surgery*, 2009;27(1):11–19.
10. Romanos GE, Nentwig GH. Diode laser (980 nm) in oral and maxillofacial surgical procedures: Clinical observations based on clinical applications. *J Clin Laser Med Surg.* 2012;30(5):321-323.
11. Gaspirc B, Skaleric U. Clinical evaluation of periodontal surgical treatment with an Er laser: 5-year results. *J Periodontol.* 2007;78(10):1864-1869.
12. Pick RM, Colvard MD. Current status of lasers in soft tissue dental surgery. *J Periodontol.* 1999;64(7):589-602.
13. Harris, D. M., Yessik, M. Therapeutic ratio quantifies laser antisepsis: ablation of *Porphyromonasgingivalis* with dental lasers. *Lasers in surgery and medicine*, 2004; 35(3):206–213.
14. Schwarz F, Putz N, Georg T, Reich E. Effect of an Er laser on periodontally involved root surfaces: an in vivo and in vitro SEM comparison. *Lasers Surg Med.* 2001;29(4):328-335.
15. Aoki, A., Mizutani, K., Taniguchi, Y., Lin, T., Ohsugi, Y., Mikami, R., Katagiri, S., Meinzer, W., Iwata, T. Current status of Er:YAG laser in periodontal surgery. *The Japanese dental science review*, 2024;60:1–14.
16. Crespi, R., Vinci, R., Capparé, P., Romanos, G. E., Gherlone, E. A clinical study of edentulous patients rehabilitated according to the "all on four" immediate function protocol. *The International journal of oral & maxillofacial implants*, 2011;27(2):428–434.
17. Aoki, A., Mizutani, K., Takasaki, A. A., Sasaki, K. M., Nagai, S., Schwarz, F., Yoshida, I., Eguro, T., Zeredo, J. L., Izumi, Y. Current status of clinical laser applications in periodontal therapy. *General dentistry*, 2008;56(7):674–767.